

EPOC returns to the NW Atlantic

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Return to Flemish Cap

Expedition M212 gears up to add important new high-resolution data to the EPOC field experiment

In September 2023, RV Meria S Merian ventured into the NW Atlantic to deploy nine oceanographic moorings across the continental slope north of Flemish Cap and south of the Grand Banks, as well as an array of compact pressure-inverted echo sounders (PIES) south of Flemish Cap. The aim of EPOC's work in this area is to measure the transport of the North Atlantic Deep Water (NADW) into and out of the Transition Zone (TZ) between the subtropical and the subpolar North Atlantic, where ocean models show a breakdown of the meridional (north-south) coherence of the AMOC.

Two years later, the German research vessel Meteor prepares to return to the region for a month-long mission to collect important new observational data from this complex and dynamic area of the Atlantic, as well as recover some of the instruments deployed two years ago.

Existing observing systems implicitly rely on the global conveyor idea, that measuring the strength of the ocean circulation at an individual latitude provides some measure of the circulation as a whole – a concept that is being challenged in EPOC. Evidence suggests substantial discontinuities in the 'conveyor belt' at key latitudes in the Atlantic, often associated with sharp changes in topography. These include locations where the deep western boundary current (DWBC) breaks away from the continental slope –

such as at the Flemish Cap. In the area around Grand Banks and Flemish Cap the warm and salty North Atlantic Current (NAC) flows northward, close to the opposing Deep Western Boundary Current (DWBC) which is colder and fresher. Together these currents form an essential part of the AMOC and contribute significantly to the transports of heat and freshwater in the North Atlantic. Interactions between the two currents potentially influence the DWBC and affect its coherence along the path around Flemish Cap and the Grand Banks.

During their month-long mission on board RV Meteor, the EPOC team – led by University of Bremen's Christian Mertens – will use a range of instruments to observe these interactions at high resolution. The data collected will add to that provided by the growing suite of EPOC instrumentation in the area, which includes current meter moorings deployed in October 2023 (and which will be recovered on a separate mission later this year), and the inverted echo sounder array which will be recovered on this expedition.

Full-depth CTD (Conductivity-Temperature-Depth) and LADCP (lowered Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler) measurements will be taken at c.100 stations along different hydrographic sections around Flemish Cap and the Grand Banks (see maps). At stations with strong vertical mixing, these measurements will be complemented by microstructure

Above, left: Bathymetric map of the M212 working area showing the planned hydrographic sections (thick red lines) (FC Flemish Cap, PASS Flemish Pass, GB Grand Banks, 47N and WOCE A02) as well as the inverted echo sounder (IES) array (red triangles) and glider deployment area (white box). Right: More detailed map showing the array of 14 inverted echo sounders (PIES and C-PIES) deployed southeast of Flemish Cap on cruise MSM121 in October 2023. The array is located at the frontal zone between the North Atlantic Current (NAC) and the Deep Western Boundary Current (DWBC).

Glider undergoing pre-deployment testing in the test basin on board RV Meteor. Mounted on top is the microstructure probe for turbulence measurements. Image courtesy C. Mertens.

profiles in the upper 1000 m of the water column using a free-falling tethered probe. The FC, PASS and GB sections are chosen to represent the upstream and downstream conditions; the 47N and A02 sections are located within TZ and will complement measurements made by the inverted echo sounder array.

Repeated CTD/LADCP profiles using a tow-yo will be made at two different locations on the continental slope with the ship moving very slowly across the bathymetry. Tow-yos are repeated casts over a defined depth range where the instruments are continuously lowered and raised while being towed by the ship at a speed of about 0.5 knots along a transect of about 20 kilometers. The resulting horizontal resolution of a few hundred meters will allow the team to identify the mechanisms that maintain lateral and vertical mixing and current-topography interactions.

And coming up later this year...

EPOC deployed nine tall current meter moorings on the continental slope of the North Atlantic Transition Zone (TZ) in 2023. The CROSSROAD-1 cruise, conducted aboard RV *Thalassa* in August 2024, subsequently enabled detailed mapping of the subtropical-subpolar TZ through the acquisition of several hydrographic sections (at both large and small scales) and microstructure profiles, and the deployment of a microstructure mooring.

Finally, ocean gliders will be used to repeatedly transverse the western boundary current and the North Atlantic Current at 47° N between 41° 30' W and 43° 30' W. The transect will span about 150 km, with a single glider requiring roughly 10 days to complete its mission. Two gliders will be deployed for 20 days, which will allow them to collect high-resolution data from four transects across the front between the two water masses. This setup enables acquisition of length-scale diagnostics that specifically target cross-frontal exchange of properties such as heat, as well as investigation of energetic characteristics within the frontal system.

The M212 expedition departs Ponta Delgada in the Azores at the end of July, working in the Flemish Cap/Grand Banks region for 4 weeks before returning to port in St John's, Newfoundland in early September. Progress during the expedition will be shared through an expedition blog – please visit www.epoc-eu.org/our-work/expeditions for details.

The upcoming CROSSROAD-2 cruise aboard RV *L'Atalante* in September-October 2025 is dedicated to the recovery of the 10 mooring lines deployed in 2023 and 2024, as well as recovery of two bottom pressure recorders for EPOC. In addition, large-scale and small-scale hydrography transects will be surveyed, sediment cores will be collected at the mooring locations, and autonomous floats (e.g., Argo and RAFOS) will be deployed.

Understanding modelled AMOC variability and its climate significance

by Brady Ferster, CERFACS

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) is a major component of the global climate system, transporting warm surface water northward and returning colder, denser water southward at depth. This circulation helps regulate Earth's climate by redistributing heat, affecting regional weather patterns, and modulating carbon storage in the ocean. However, the AMOC is not constant, it varies over time due to both internal climate dynamics and external influences such as greenhouse gas emissions. Understanding how this variability operates, particularly on decadal-to-multidecadal and centennial timescales, is crucial for interpreting past climate changes and improving future projections.

In a recently-published study (Ferster et al., 2025 - see details at the end of this article), EPOC researcher Brady Ferster and colleagues investigate AMOC variability using a combination of targeted simulations with the IPSL-CM6A-LR climate model and long pre-industrial control runs from 37 models in the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6). They focus on two dominant timescales of variability: decadal-to-multidecadal variability (15–65 years) and centennial variability (over 65 years).

In the IPSL-CM6A-LR model, decadal-to-multidecadal variability is primarily driven by temperature-related changes in ocean density in the western subpolar North Atlantic, particularly in the Labrador and Irminger Seas. Critically, the amplitude of decadal-to-multidecadal variability increases linearly with the mean strength of the AMOC. That is, stronger AMOC mean states lead to larger decadal fluctuations. This relationship is clearly illustrated in Figure 2a of the study (see below) and remains consistent across a range of experiments in which the mean AMOC state is altered remotely through changes in tropical Indian Ocean sea surface temperatures. This experimental setup allows the researchers to isolate changes in AMOC variability without directly disturbing surface heat or freshwater fluxes in the North Atlantic, preserving realistic air–sea interactions. Centennial variability in the IPSL-CM6A-LR model, by contrast, is driven mainly by salinity anomalies in the same subpolar region. While centennial variability also increases with AMOC strength in IPSL-CM6A-LR, this pattern does not hold across models in CMIP6.

The analysis of the broader CMIP6 ensemble shows a clear and consistent relationship between mean AMOC strength and the amplitude of decadal-to-multidecadal variability across models (Figure 4a). This suggests that decadal-to-multidecadal variability scaling may serve as a robust feature of coupled models and could help evaluate model performance against observed estimates of mean AMOC

strength. In contrast, there is no consistent scaling between AMOC strength and centennial variability across the CMIP6 ensemble (Figure 4b). The presence and amplitude of centennial variability differ substantially among models, depending on structural characteristics such as ocean resolution, sea ice processes, and climatological background states. Notably, only a subset of models, particularly those using the NEMO ocean component like IPSL, CNRM, and EC-Earth exhibit strong centennial variability, often attributed to Arctic-origin salinity anomalies and long-timescale ocean–ice feedbacks. This underscores the more model-dependent nature of centennial variability and highlights the uncertainty in its underlying mechanisms.

These findings carry several key implications for future research. First, the dependence of variability on the AMOC mean state is critical. If climate change alters the mean state of the AMOC, then the character and amplitude of AMOC variability are also likely to evolve. This would mean that variability is not stationary but shifts over time, potentially altering climate impacts associated with the AMOC, such as regional temperature and precipitation patterns.

Second, the mechanisms driving centennial variability remain poorly understood and vary across models. While salinity anomalies in the subpolar North Atlantic play a central role in IPSL-CM6A-LR, the source of Arctic sea ice melt, freshwater transport, or interactions with the Southern Ocean differs between models. Because centennial variability operates on timescales longer than many model simulations, it remains difficult to isolate and constrain.

Third, if variability depends on the mean state, as these findings indicate, it adds another layer of uncertainty to future climate scenarios. Since the AMOC mean state is influenced by anthropogenic forcing, feedbacks such as sea ice loss and freshwater input may significantly alter not only the strength but also the variability of the AMOC. Models that simulate different future AMOC states may thus diverge in both the magnitude and character of variability. This reinforces the need to evaluate models against observed ocean properties, such as heat content, salinity patterns, and overturning strength, and improve physical processes controlling those features.

Within the EPOC project, ongoing work is addressing these challenges. One area of research focuses on understanding the coherence of AMOC across different latitudes, using both observations and model diagnostics to identify where variability originates and how it propagates. Another

Left: Figure 2a from Ferster et al. (2025). The amplitude of the AMOC decadal-to-multidecadal and centennial variability versus the AMOC mean strength in the IPSL-CM6A-LR experiments. Variability is estimated through a 15–65 years bandpass filter and a 65-year lowpass filter applied to the AMOC timeseries.

Above: Figure 4 from Ferster et al. (2025). Similar to Figure 2a, but for 37 CMIP6 pre-industrial control simulations. (a) Amplitudes of decadal-to-multidecadal and (b) centennial variability plotted against the mean AMOC strength. At the 99% confidence level, there is a significant relationship with decadal-to-multidecadal variability. Only models with at least 300 years of available data are considered and the timeseries are detrended before the analysis.

effort compares modeled mean states to a wide range of observational benchmarks, including surface temperature and salinity, meridional heat transport, and streamfunction structure. These comparisons help identify persistent model biases and inform targeted improvements in model physics. Finally, dedicated experiments are being used to explore how resolution, vertical mixing, and freshwater processes shape AMOC behavior and contribute to uncertainty in projections.

In summary, Ferster et al. (2025) demonstrate that AMOC variability, especially on decadal-to-multidecadal timescales, is strongly influenced by the mean state of the circulation. This relationship is consistent across many models and may offer a physical constraint for evaluating near-term variability. In contrast, centennial variability remains model-dependent and uncertain, underscoring the need for extended simulations and deeper understanding of the physical mechanisms involved. Addressing these questions will be vital for refining regional and global climate predictions and managing long-term climate risks.

Read the full article:

Ferster BS, Fedorov AV, Mignot J & Guilyardi E. (2025) AMOC Variability in Climate Models and Its Dependence on the Mean State. *Geophysical Research Letters*. DOI: [10.1029/2024GL110356](https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL110356)

Project VERIFY: An early warning system for climate tipping points

Climate tipping points are crucial thresholds in the Earth's system: once crossed, they can trigger significant and often irreversible changes. However, predicting these tipping points is a major challenge, and past models have struggled to fully capture the complex interactions that drive them. A new project, funded through the UK's Advanced Research + Innovation Agency (ARIA), aims to develop an early warning system for climate tipping points by using advanced modelling techniques to analyse past climate data.

Project VERIFY will use a combination of AI, palaeoclimate data and next-generation observation techniques to make climate forecasting more accurate, reliable, and actionable than ever before. A key component of this work is the development of Digital Twins of past tipping points – highly detailed computer simulations trained on real-world data – that can be used to test the reliability of early warning signals.

EPOC researcher David Thornalley (UCL) is a co-lead on VERIFY, contributing expertise in reconstructing past oceanic and climate conditions to integrate palaeoclimate observations into these predictive models. This will help refine early warning systems for major climate shifts, which include changes in the Greenland Ice Sheet and the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre – both crucial for global climate regulation. Other EPOC researchers involved in this groundbreaking project include Joel Hirschi (NOC) and Jack Wharton (UCL).

David explains: "Crossing a tipping point in the North Atlantic Subpolar Gyre would alter UK climate and have severe repercussions for our biodiversity, food security, agriculture, and more. In Project VERIFY we will make use of real-world examples of past tipping points to better understand these events and to test how well any early warning systems are performing."

Project VERIFY will generate the first model runs for paleoclimate time intervals using such a high-resolution coupled climate model with interactive ice sheets and the very high resolution ocean-only NEMO model. Although VERIFY is focused on the Greenland Ice Sheet and North Atlantic Sub-polar Gyre, the open-access model runs will be available for investigating AMOC so many of the ideas explored in EPOC can be extended and tested here.

Project VERIFY is part of ARIA's £81 million Forecasting Tipping Points programme, which will unite 27 international teams in a collaborative effort to detect the earliest signs of climate tipping points. It started on 1 April 2025 and will run for 5 years, with a budget of £5.27 million.

Right: Summary schematic of Project VERIFY's approach

ASOF 2025 Highlights: Connecting EPOC's Arctic research to a broader climate context

ASOF
23rd Arctic-Subarctic Ocean Fluxes Workshop
13-15 May, 2025, Barcelona, Spain

by Rebecca McPherson (AWI), Till Baumann (IMR),
Hege-Beate Fredriksen (NPI) & Laura de Steur (NPI)

The Arctic-Subarctic Ocean Fluxes (ASOF) program is an international initiative focused on understanding the role of the Arctic and Subarctic oceans in the climate system. The ASOF community concentrates on measuring and modelling the variability of mass, heat, freshwater, and ice fluxes in these high-latitude regions and quantifying key processes governing the variability and connections between the regions. The synthesis of observations, modelling efforts and process understanding are essential to understanding how the Arctic-Subarctic region influences climate variability across the globe, and vice versa.

This year's ASOF annual workshop, hosted by the Instituto de Ciencias del Mar (ICM) in Barcelona during 13-15 May, 2025, provided a valuable forum to connect the work of EPOC's Arctic subgroup with the wider Arctic-Subarctic research community. More than 100 scientists from around the world attended in person, with additional participants joining online. Over three days, a wide range of presentations and poster sessions covered research across the Subpolar North Atlantic, the Nordic Seas, the key Arctic gateways, as well as the central Arctic Ocean.

EPOC was well represented throughout the workshop, reflecting the importance of the Arctic as the northernmost extension of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) — and a region where climate change is progressing nearly four times faster than the global average. Several EPOC researchers presented new results focused on Fram Strait, the main oceanic gateway between the Arctic Ocean and the North Atlantic. Wilken-Jon von Appen (AWI) and Laura de Steur (NPI) shared updates on the inflow and outflow through Fram Strait respectively, using long-term moored observations to provide up-to-date estimates of boundary currents on seasonal to multi-annual timescales. Key findings included a clear warming trend in the West Spitsbergen Current over the past 27 years — with evidence going back to 1969 — impacting the transport of oceanic heat into the Arctic. On the western side of Fram Strait, results showed that the freshwater transport of the East Greenland

Current has been declining since 1992 to 2019, however a reversal of that trend occurred in 2020 due to an increase in both freshwater content and southward flow. Overall, the total freshwater transport is by now, dominated by the liquid part and sea ice plays a much smaller role. Increases in the ocean heat transported to the Arctic add to the total Arctic warming, while changes in sea-ice cover and freshwater input can have an imprint on the AMOC.

Till Baumann (IMR) examined the upstream origins of the warm inflow into Fram Strait and the Barents Sea via the Norwegian Atlantic Current (NwAC), using three decades of repeated observations along key transects. The NwAC is a vital branch of the AMOC, transporting heat northward through the Nordic Seas. Till's research explored the physical drivers behind observed variability and changes in heat transport, offering new insights into the dynamic connection between the Arctic, Fram Strait, and the broader North Atlantic system. Rebecca McPherson (AWI) then presented the downstream impacts of such variability. She identified a new mechanism that drives temperature fluctuations in the West Spitsbergen Current, tracing the advection of these anomalies across Fram Strait to Northeast Greenland's glaciers. There, ocean heat is shown to directly drive melt rates at the glacier's grounding line — where the ice meets the ocean bed.

Expanding beyond Fram Strait, Hege-Beate Fredriksen (NPI) presented a status update of the pan-Arctic inverse model effort, which integrates observations from all four major Arctic gateways: Fram Strait, the Barents Sea Opening, Bering Strait, and Davis Strait. Drawing on data from the long-term mooring arrays and hydrographic surveys, this model aims to provide comprehensive estimates of net pan-Arctic heat, freshwater, and volume fluxes and quantify Arctic overturning. Her work is a key step toward closing the Arctic budget and understanding how the region responds to ongoing warming of the global climate.

The next ASOF meeting is planned for Bergen, Norway, in 2026, where the community will continue building on these vital efforts to monitor and model the changing Arctic gateways, and its impacts on the AMOC.

Left: EPOC researchers in action at ASOF - from top, Laura de Steur (NPI), Till Baumann (IMR), Rebecca McPherson (AWI) and Hege-Beate Fredriksen (NPI). Images courtesy L. de Steur, H-B. Fredriksen and R. McPherson.

Below: EPOC researchers at the ASOF workshop (L-R): Till Baumann (IMR), Laura de Steur (NPI), Rebecca McPherson (AWI) and Hege-Beate Fredriksen (NPI). Image courtesy L. de Steur.

EPOC looks forward to welcoming new partners

In 2023 the EU launched a new mechanism to support wider inclusivity in Horizon Europe projects, with calls for proposals closing in September 2023 and 2024. This 'Hop-On Facility' allows organisations from low R&I performing countries to join ongoing research and innovation projects, subject to the agreement of the respective consortium. The main selection criteria are excellence and added value of the new partner performing a relevant new task in the project.

EPOC grasped this opportunity to expand the project partnership, and applied for the 'EPOC Hop-On' grant, which has now been positively evaluated by the EU. The inclusion of Havstovan (Faroe Marine Research Institute) as a new EPOC partner will allow inclusion of time series data on the main exchanges across the Greenland-Scotland Ridge, as well as investigation of possibilities to close the largest gap in the existing observational system. The aim is to obtain a better understanding of the link between this AMOC chokepoint and other AMOC components.

The Greenland-Scotland Ridge is a submarine ridge system that acts as a partial barrier between the Arctic Mediterranean (Nordic Seas and Arctic Ocean) and the Atlantic Ocean. Across the ridge there is an upper layer inflow of warm and saline Atlantic water to the Arctic Mediterranean, which keeps large areas free of sea ice, helps maintain a mild climate and provides good living conditions for large fisheries resources. According to observations¹, around 30% of this inflow leaves the Arctic Mediterranean as a surface outflow on both sides of Greenland. The remaining 70% is converted into cold and dense 'overflow' water that flows from the Arctic Mediterranean into the Atlantic through the deep passages across the ridge. With a total volume transport around 6 Sv (1 Sv = 106 m³/s), the overflow contributes about one third of the water that ends up flowing southwards through the

western Atlantic as the deep limb of the AMOC. The overflow water is considerably denser than any other water mass in the North Atlantic and therefore plays a disproportionally large role in maintaining the density contrast between the upper and deep limbs of the AMOC.

Together with other institutes, Havstovan has monitored the Atlantic inflows between Iceland and Scotland and the Faroe Bank Channel (FBC) overflow that passes through the FBC for almost three decades. The results show a remarkable stability in volume transports together with increasing temperatures for these flows^{2,3}. EPOC Hop-On activities will extend and refine observational records by re-analysing historical observations. This will provide high-quality time series for the two main Atlantic inflows (the IF-inflow and the FS-inflow) and the two main overflows (DS-overflow and FBC-overflow; see map below).

Additionally, EPOC Hop-On activities will provide the basis for designing a monitoring system for the overflow across the Iceland-Faroe Ridge (IFR overflow). This overflow branch has been known for more than a century and transport values as high as 1 Sv have been suggested, but neither the average transport, nor its variations are reliably known. Through a series of dedicated experiments 2020–2023, the main overflow locations on the ridge have been identified (unpublished data, Havstovan), but monitoring the IFR overflow on top of the ridge will be logistically very difficult and expensive. Instead, it has been suggested⁴ that the overflow from a large part of the ridge is collected at a downstream location over the south-east Icelandic slope where a persistent bottom-intensified current has been observed⁵. EPOC Hop-On will deploy instrumentation along a section crossing this current and at a key location on the ridge with the aim to design a monitoring system for the IFR overflow.

Following a positive proposal evaluation, the EPOC Hop-On grant is currently under negotiation with the EU.

References: ¹Østerhus, S. et al. (2019) DOI:10.5194/os-15-379-2019; ²Larsen, K. M. H. et al. (2024) DOI: 10.1029/2024GL110097; ³Hansen, B. et al. (2023) DOI: 10.5194/os-19-1225-2023; ⁴Beaird, N. L. et al. (2013) DOI: 10.1175/JPOD-13-029.1; ⁵Olsen, S. M. et al. (2016) DOI: 10.5194/os-12-545-2016.

Left: The Greenland-Scotland Ridge. Grey areas are shallower than 750 m. Red arrows show the three Atlantic inflow branches. White arrows show the overflow branches. Average transport values are based on observations (Østerhus et al., 2019). The black line and the black circle labelled 'EPOC' indicate mooring locations in an experiment aimed at establishing a monitoring system for the overflow across the Iceland-Faroe Ridge, the 'IFR-overflow'.

Ocean policy scene

by Vikki Gunn, Seascope Consultants

Above: Various research/expedition vessels bask in the sunshine in Nice harbour during UNOC3. From left: the Norwegian Statsraad Lehmkuhl; the Santa Maria Manuela yacht used for expeditions by the Oceano Azul Foundation; OceanX's OceanXplorer; the French RV Thalassa, and at the far end with the red funnel, the German RV Meteor. Image courtesy V. Gunn.

Recent weeks have seen a number of ocean policy events take place, with a focus around the [third UN Ocean Conference](#) (UNOC3) which took place in Nice, France on 9-13 June 2025. This event, convened by the UN to chart progress toward Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 14 – *Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development* – was jointly chaired by France and Costa Rica, and marked the third conference in the series, since its inception in 2017. With the overarching theme of 'Accelerating action and mobilizing all actors to conserve and sustainably use the Ocean', the event drew 14,000 participants from 175 country delegations, UN agencies, IGOs, the science community and civil society.

The build-up to this widely-anticipated gathering of the ocean community included three special events in the region during the preceding week, including the [One Ocean Science Congress](#) (OOSC; 4-6 June 2025) – an event that aimed to provide Heads of State, Government and broader society with comprehensive scientific insights on the Ocean's health and future trajectory. OOSC produced 10 recommendations from its 33 roundtable discussions, 500+ oral presentations and 2000 attendees. Other special events ahead of UNOC3 included the [Ocean Rise and Coastal Resilience Summit](#), aimed at uniting coastal cities and small island developing states (SIDS) in the common goal of addressing climate impacts and sea-level rise; and the [Blue Economy and Finance Forum](#) (BEFF), which sought to secure new partnerships and financial commitments to the blue economy. On a more informal note, a public science festival took place in Villefranche-Sur-Mer on 7-13 June 2025.

Also ahead of UNOC3, the European Commission announced the launch of its new [Ocean Pact](#) – a “comprehensive strategy to better protect the ocean, promote a thriving blue economy and support the well-being of people living in coastal areas”. Bringing together the EU's policies and actions related to the ocean, it aims to create a unified and coordinated plan for managing the ocean and is constructed around six priorities: i) protecting and restoring ocean health; ii) boosting the competitiveness of the EU sustainable blue economy; iii) supporting coastal and island communities, and outermost regions; iv) advancing ocean research, knowledge, skills and innovation; v) enhancing maritime security and defence, and vi) strengthening EU ocean diplomacy and international ocean governance.

But what of progress and outcomes from UNOC3? The official UNOC3 programme comprised 7 plenary sessions and 10 thematic Ocean Action Panels that focused discussion on hot topics such as the conservation, sustainable management and restoration of ocean ecosystems; increasing marine scientific cooperation and capacity; ocean finance; marine pollution; sustainable fisheries management and food security; maritime transport; the ocean, climate, and biodiversity nexus; and ocean governance. In addition, some 450+ side events took place within the conference grounds and at venues across the city, including at the La Baleine publicly accessible zone. A number of research vessels, including RV *Meteor* and RV *Thalassa* as well as the privately-owned *OceanXplorer*, also provided a novel space for special events in the secure zone of Nice harbour.

A key headline during the week – and the source of much speculation, excitement and anticipation among delegates

– was progress by countries to ratify the new UN legally-binding treaty on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity beyond national jurisdiction (known as the [BBNJ Agreement](#)). Following its adoption in June 2023, the treaty entered a phase of ratification whereby countries confirm their readiness to be legally bound by the Agreement; 60 countries are required to ratify the treaty for it to enter into force. During the Conference, 19 formal ratifications were submitted, bringing the total to 50 (+ the EU) with a number of additional countries indicating significant progress towards ratification. Not quite the full 60 that some observers were hoping for during UNOC3, but solid and significant progress towards treaty ratification.

Progress towards the UN Convention on Biological Diversity's [Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework](#) targets was also at the forefront of the conference agenda, in particular the '30x30' target of achieving protection of 30% of the global ocean by 2030. A particularly noteworthy announcement came from French Polynesia and their plans to create the world's largest marine protected area (MPA). At 4.8 million km², it covers the whole of their EEZ and includes just over 1 million km² of highly or fully protected ocean, an area twice the size of mainland France. Other countries pledging to significantly expand protected areas in their waters included Chile, Colombia and Portugal, and the UK announced a consultation on banning bottom trawling fishing practices in its English MPAs.

Other headline topics included progress towards concluding the difficult negotiations on the [ocean plastics treaty](#), the ongoing debate around deep-sea mining and the growing coalition of States calling for a moratorium on it, and progress towards ratification of the new [Agreement on Fisheries Subsidies](#) under the World Trade Organization which now requires only a handful more ratifications to enter into force.

Of particular interest to the ocean observing and modelling community was the launch of the [10,000 Ships for the Ocean](#) programme - a partnership with the shipping industry to scale-up global ocean observations and become a key contributor to the [Global Ocean Observing System](#) (GOOS). This initiative aims, by 2035, to scale up the current fleet of 2,000 ships to 10,000 commercial vessels providing real-time weather and surface ocean data to GOOS. The initiative complements an ongoing push to reform the Argo float programme, in which 1,200 new floats will be deployed by 2030 to monitor the ocean to 6,000 m depth, as well as expanding the range of physical and chemical parameters that are measured.

After a frenetic week, the UNOC3 showcase culminated in a conference Declaration entitled '*Our Ocean, Our Future: United for Urgent Action*' and the conference closed with a general vibe of optimism, but with the sobering recognition that a tremendous amount of heavy lifting lies ahead in order to meet international goals and targets.

However, the ocean policy action didn't end there... many high-level delegates made their way from Nice to Bonn, Germany to join climate colleagues for the [Annual Ocean and Climate Change Dialogue](#) (17-18 June 2025), convened as part of the Bonn Climate Change Conference under the auspices of the [UN Framework Convention on Climate Change](#) (UNFCCC). This meeting provides a forum to discuss ocean-climate issues ahead of the 30th Conference of the Parties ([COP30](#)), which takes place in Belém, Brazil in November this year. Constructed around three expert panels and subsequent discussion sessions, the Dialogue agenda focused on ocean-based measures in nationally determined contributions (NDCs – countries' committed actions to meet emissions reduction targets under the Paris Agreement), the ocean's role in the Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA), and ocean-climate-biodiversity synergies.

So, after this marathon series of events in June, what's coming up next on the ocean policy horizon this year? July sees the [International Seabed Authority](#) (ISA) convening its various committees, Council and Assembly to continue discussions on the draft regulations for deep-sea mineral exploitation.

In August, the International Negotiating Committee for the UN Plastics Treaty will meet in Geneva in an attempt to break through the deadlock in negotiations that has so far prevented an Agreement being reached. Later in August the second meeting of the Preparatory Commission for the BBNJ Agreement will be convened at the UN headquarters in New York, where more of the fine detail missing from the treaty text will be discussed. The nature of that meeting will hinge on whether the Agreement has been ratified by then – with only 9 more ratifications now required for the treaty to enter into force, all eyes are on the race for 60.

And in November, UNFCCC COP30 will take place in Brazil with six wide-ranging themes dominating the agenda: i) reducing greenhouse gas emissions; ii) adaptation to climate change; iii) climate finance for developing countries; iv) renewable energy technologies and low-carbon solutions; v) preserving forests and biodiversity, and vi) climate justice and the social impacts of climate change.

About EPOC

EPOC (Explaining and Predicting the Ocean Conveyor) is a 5-year research project funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe programme. Involving 21 institutions from France, Germany, Norway, UK, USA and Canada, and led by Universität Hamburg, EPOC aims to generate a new concept of the Atlantic meridional overturning circulation (AMOC), its function in the Earth system and how it impacts weather and climate.

EPOC has five overarching scientific objectives:

- Generate comprehensive records of AMOC transports across the whole Atlantic, to assess the timescales of transport variability and the degree to which the AMOC behaves as a conveyor belt.
- Determine key processes that make or break meridional connectivity of ocean transports, and assess their representation in models, especially in high resolution coupled simulations.
- Identify the processes and drivers of recent change in the AMOC, and infer the likely roles of natural and anthropogenic forcings, and internal variability.
- Assess the key processes of future AMOC changes, and identify indicators of abrupt changes and AMOC-related climate impacts with societal relevance.
- Design, and deploy elements of, a next generation observing system for the entire system of the AMOC.

 [EPOC Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/epoc-project)